

On Unprecise Numbers

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Regarding computability, there are three kinds of real numbers: the computable, the random, and the unprecise numbers. Some unprecise numbers are those based on Radó's busy beaver functions, Chaitin's constant Ω , Turing's uncomputable number δ , and those coding the halting problem oracle of a Turing complete language. All these unprecise numbers are complete, because they can only be defined in a Turing complete language, but we prove, against one of Turing's intuitions, that not every complete number is unprecise. We also show that, while a rational number can be coded into a string, a real number has to be coded into a set of strings, and thus an unprecise number is any coded into a semidecidable set.

Keywords: uncomputable number, unprecise number, complete number, halting theorem, Turing completeness.

§1 Introduction

¶1 · Turing (1936) showed that the computable numbers are enumerable when Cantor (1891) had already shown that the real numbers cannot be enumerated. Both together imply that there are infinitely many more uncomputable real numbers than computable numbers. However, in practice, we do not use any uncomputable number. Why? And what does this mean?

¶2 · It means that, if we choose randomly a real number, the probability of selecting a computable one is zero. Then, it seems that the uncomputable numbers are the random real numbers. So we use them, frequently, though not any one of them specifically. However, as we will see, that is not the whole story.

$$\text{Real} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Computable} \\ \text{Uncomputable} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Unprecise} \\ \text{Random} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$$

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§2 Two examples

¶1 · Perhaps we do not use any specific uncomputable number, but surely we can find them, can't we? Well, we know of some impossible computations, conspicuously that which solves the halting problem, defined by [Davis \(1958\)](#). Therefore, should computing a number required that we had solved the halting problem, or that we had performed any other uncomputable task, then that number would be uncomputable.

¶2 · For example,

$$B = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} 2^{-S(n)} = 2^{-1} + 2^{-6} + 2^{-21} + 2^{-107} + \dots$$

$$\approx 0.1000010000000000000000100000000000_2$$

is an uncomputable number since, to compute it completely, with arbitrary precision, we would need to solve the halting problem. $S(n)$ is the busy beaver maximum shifts function, an uncomputable function defined by [Radó \(1962\)](#) as the maximum number of steps of all halting computations that a Turing machine with n states and only two symbols (blank and another one) starting on a blank tape can perform. Notice that this number B does not represent the halting problem as such, but somehow it is only a very peculiar representation of the halting problem of a very specific computing machine on a very special case.

¶3 · Fixing the number of symbols to two, the number of states of a Turing machine determines the size of its table. And, see [Casares \(G\)](#), a program is a coded Turing machine table that a particular universal Turing machine can interpret. Then, the number of states n is related to the program length $|\mathfrak{p}|$, used for example in [Chaitin's \(1975\)](#) constant, where $\mathfrak{p}\downarrow$ denotes that program \mathfrak{p} halts when it starts on an blank tape:

$$\Omega = \sum_{\substack{\mathfrak{p} \in \mathfrak{P} \\ \mathfrak{p}\downarrow}} 2^{-|\mathfrak{p}|} .$$

Chaitin's constant Ω is another uncomputable real number. But this number Ω , and any other that uses programs instead of machines, represents the halting problem even more indirectly than B , since it is also mediated by a coding, which is a particular prefix one in the case of Ω . So this number Ω does not represent the halting problem as such, but somehow it is only a very peculiar representation of the halting problem of a very specific computing machine on a very special case and very particularly coded.

¶4 · Both B and Ω are different from a random number, as for example a binary random number built by flipping a coin to select each of its bits. The difference is that, while we cannot compute any bit of a *random number*, we can compute some of the bits of B , as shown above, and of Ω , but not all of them. The reason behind this is that the set of the halting computations is computably enumerable, while truly random sequences are not.

¶5 · In order to see this in detail, we need some preparation, but since it requires more than one paragraph, it will be the matter of the next section.

§3 The halting set is computably enumerable

¶1 · Given an enumeration of a non-empty finite set of non-blank symbols Γ , and every finite set is computably enumerable, we can compute an enumeration of the infinite set Γ^* of all finite strings drawn from that ordered set of symbols. For instance and canonically, using the shortlex order.

DEFINITION: In the *shortlex order*, strings are primarily sorted by length, with the shortest strings first, and strings of the same length are sorted into lexicographical order, done on the enumeration of the finite set of symbols.

COMMENT: The shortlex order defines a bijection between the strings and the natural numbers, $\# : \Gamma^* \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$. For instance, the empty string $\langle \rangle$ corresponds to zero, and the converse, so $\#\langle \rangle = 0$ and $\#^{-1}(0) = \langle \rangle$.

¶2 · Below, we will need to compute an enumeration of the Cartesian product of two infinite sets that are both computably enumerable. The trick is not having to complete one before starting the other one. The triangular enumeration, also known as Cantor pairing function, which is a bijection $\nabla : \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$, is the canonical way of doing it.

DEFINITION: Let $a_0, a_1, a_2, a_3 \dots$ be an enumeration of set A , and $b_0, b_1, b_2, b_3 \dots$ be an enumeration of set B . Then the *triangular enumeration* of $A \times B$ is:

$$(a_0, b_0); (a_0, b_1), (a_1, b_0); (a_0, b_2), (a_1, b_1), (a_2, b_0); (a_0, b_3), (a_1, b_2), (a_2, b_1), (a_3, b_0); \dots$$

In other words, pair (a_x, b_y) is pair number i , p_i , where:

$$\begin{aligned} i &= \nabla(x, y) = x + \frac{(x + y)(x + y + 1)}{2}, \\ s &= \nabla_s^{-1}(i) = \left\lfloor \frac{-1 + \sqrt{8i + 1}}{2} \right\rfloor, \\ x &= \nabla_x^{-1}(i) = i - \frac{s(s + 1)}{2}, \\ y &= \nabla_y^{-1}(i) = s - x. \end{aligned}$$

¶3 · DEFINITION: To define computation, we need the *equation of Turing completeness*, see Casares (G):

$$\exists \mathcal{U}, \forall \mathcal{P}, \forall \mathfrak{d} : \overleftarrow{\mathcal{U}\langle \mathfrak{p} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}} \rangle} = \mathcal{P}\langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle,$$

where:

- \mathcal{P} is a Turing machine,
- $\mathfrak{d} \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^*$ is an input string to \mathcal{P} ,
- $\mathcal{P}\langle \mathfrak{d} \rangle \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^*$ is the corresponding output string, or $\infty \notin \Gamma_{\mathcal{P}}^*$ if it does not halt,
- \mathcal{U} is a universal Turing machine,
- $\vec{\mathfrak{d}} \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ is the string \mathfrak{d} coded in the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} ,
- $\mathfrak{p} \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ is the *program* that codes \mathcal{P} in the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} , so $\mathfrak{p} = \vec{\mathcal{P}}$,
- the $|$ represents an end of program symbol or, in general, the composing operation of the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} , as **cons** or **Merge**,
- $\mathcal{U}\langle \mathfrak{p} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}} \rangle \in \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ is the output string of \mathcal{U} , which is coded in the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} , or $\infty \notin \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ if it does not halt, and
- the left pointing arrow on top denotes the corresponding decoding, $\overleftarrow{\mathfrak{d}} = \mathfrak{d}$, which leaves ∞ unchanged, $\overleftarrow{\infty} = \infty$.

¶4 · DEFINITION: Any language implemented by a universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} that satisfies the equation of Turing completeness is a *complete language*, denoted \mathcal{L} , also known as a Turing complete language.

DEFINITION: In the complete language \mathcal{L} implemented by the universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} , the string between angled quotes $\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{\mathbf{d}} \rangle$ expresses \mathbf{c} , which is the *computation* that applies coded data $\vec{\mathbf{d}}$ to program \mathbf{p} .

DEFINITION: The *halting set* is the set of all halting computations.

¶5 · Note that, while in the right hand side of the equation of Turing completeness, \mathbf{d} is any string of symbols of \mathcal{P} , in the left hand side, what is on the tape is not any string of symbols of \mathcal{U} , but a well-formed formula, or sentence, of the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} . Therefore, the equation of Turing completeness requires parsing the left hand side string between angled quotes, implying that it has to be always possible to decide

- whether a string of \mathcal{U} is a well-formed formula $\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{\mathbf{d}} \rangle$ of \mathcal{L} or not,

which requires to be always possible to decide both:

- whether a string of \mathcal{U} is a program \mathbf{p} of \mathcal{L} or not, and
- whether a string of \mathcal{U} is properly coded data $\vec{\mathbf{d}}$ of \mathcal{L} or not.

In other words, the *syntax* of the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} , which is the set of its sentences, denoted $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$, is decidable. And, since the sentences of \mathcal{L} are computations, $\mathbf{c} = \langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{\mathbf{d}} \rangle$, the semantics of a complete language expresses computations; the meaning of sentence $\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{\mathbf{d}} \rangle$ is $\mathcal{P}(\mathbf{d})$. But, because we are finite, we can only reach the meaning of the halting computations, so for us *semantics*, denoted $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$, is the halting set. We will call any non-halting computation a *paradox*, implying that paradoxes are syntactically correct sentences that do not belong to semantics.

¶6 · THEOREM 1: *The set of all computations is computably enumerable.*

PROOF: The syntax of the language \mathcal{L} implemented by \mathcal{U} is decidable, and every well-formed formula of \mathcal{L} is a computation. Therefore the set of all computations is decidable, and then, as shown by Post (1944), both itself and its complement (in the set of all strings of symbols of \mathcal{U}) are computably enumerable. QED

COMMENT: Practically, we can enumerate the finite strings of \mathcal{U} using the shortlex order. Then we can order the set of programs, thus. Take the next string in the enumeration of the strings of \mathcal{U} , and determine whether it is a program of \mathcal{L} or not: if it is, append it to the enumeration of programs and go to the next one; if it is not, discard it and go to the next one. Similarly, we can order the set of coded strings. And now, given the enumeration of programs and the enumeration of coded data strings, we can use the triangular enumeration to build the enumeration of computations.

¶7 · THEOREM 2: *The set of all halting computations is computably enumerable.*

PROOF: Since the set of computations is computably enumerable, by THEOREM 1, let us denote computation number c as \mathbf{c}_c . Now we define the set of runnings as the Cartesian product of the set of computations and the natural numbers. Then the generic *running* is the ordered pair (\mathbf{c}_c, s) , where s represents a number of computing steps, so $s \in \mathbb{N}$ with its natural order. We evaluate (\mathbf{c}_c, s) to 1 if computation \mathbf{c}_c has halted after running its first s steps, and to 0 otherwise. Finally, we build the triangular enumeration of runnings and, every time we get a pair (\mathbf{c}_c, s) that evaluates to 1, we append \mathbf{c}_c to the enumeration of the halting computations, if it was not already in. QED

COMMENT: In fewer words, *the halting set is computably enumerable*. Or, in even less words, *semantics is computably enumerable*.

§4 Halting theorem

¶1 · Without loss of generality, we will use the complete language \mathcal{L} implemented by the universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} with its canonical enumerations $\#$ and ∇ for the proof of the *halting theorem*; its first version is in Turing (1936) §8, see §5.3.

THEOREM 3: *No program can decide for every computation whether it will halt or not.*

¶2 · PROOF: Just before THEOREM 1, we have already seen:

- that the set of coded strings $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\vec{d}}$ is decidable and then computably enumerable, so we will refer to coded string number d as \vec{d}_d ;
- that the set of programs $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\mathbf{p}}$ is decidable and then computably enumerable, so we will refer to program number p as \mathbf{p}_p ; and
- that the set of computations $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$ is decidable and then computably enumerable, so we could refer to computation number c as \mathbf{c}_c , where $\mathbf{c}_c = \langle \mathbf{p}_p | \vec{d}_d \rangle$ if $c = \nabla(p, d)$.

¶3 · We will set a Cantor's diagonal argument to show that there is not any Turing machine \mathcal{H} that takes any arbitrary computation as input and every time it outputs, in a finite number of computing steps, a string expressing whether the computation will halt or not, say the string \vec{d}_1 if it will halt, and \vec{d}_0 if it will not halt.

$$\nexists \mathcal{H}, \forall \mathbf{p}, \forall \vec{d} \begin{cases} \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{d} \rangle = \vec{d}_1 & \text{if } \mathcal{U}\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{d} \rangle \neq \infty \\ \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{d} \rangle = \vec{d}_0 & \text{if } \mathcal{U}\langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{d} \rangle = \infty \end{cases}$$

¶4 · Now, for the sake of the argument, let us assume that \mathcal{H} exists. Then the following matrix of \vec{d}_1 and \vec{d}_0 string values could be computed (without got stuck in a non-halting computation) using the triangular enumeration ∇ on every computation.

$$\begin{array}{cccccc} \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_0 | \vec{d}_0 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_0 | \vec{d}_1 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_0 | \vec{d}_2 \rangle & \dots & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_0 | \vec{d}_d \rangle & \dots \\ \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_1 | \vec{d}_0 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_1 | \vec{d}_1 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_1 | \vec{d}_2 \rangle & \dots & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_1 | \vec{d}_d \rangle & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots \\ \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_p | \vec{d}_0 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_p | \vec{d}_1 \rangle & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_p | \vec{d}_2 \rangle & \dots & \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_p | \vec{d}_d \rangle & \dots \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots \end{array}$$

However, the row for program \mathbf{q} , which negates the diagonal, would not be in the matrix.

$$\mathbf{q} : \forall n \in \mathbb{N} \begin{cases} \mathcal{U}\langle \mathbf{q} | \vec{d}_n \rangle = \vec{d}_1 & \text{if } \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_n | \vec{d}_n \rangle = \vec{d}_0 \\ \mathcal{U}\langle \mathbf{q} | \vec{d}_n \rangle = \infty & \text{if } \mathcal{H}\langle \mathbf{p}_n | \vec{d}_n \rangle = \vec{d}_1 \end{cases}$$

Since, $\forall p \in \mathbb{N}$, $\mathbf{q} \neq \mathbf{p}_p$, then program \mathbf{q} cannot exist. But program \mathbf{q} would exist if the program for \mathcal{H} , denoted \mathbf{h} , existed, which would be the case if \mathcal{H} existed as assumed. Therefore, the assumption was false.

¶5 · Then, in the complete language \mathcal{L} of the universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} , a program \mathbf{h} that decides for every computation whether or not it will halt cannot exist. QED

¶6 · COROLLARY: The halting theorem says that *the halting set is undecidable*. Therefore, *in every complete language \mathcal{L} , syntax $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$ is decidable but semantics $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ is undecidable*.

COMMENT: In terms of Post (1944), the halting set $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ is computably enumerable, but not its complement. Neither its complement in the set of strings, $\Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^* \setminus \Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$, nor its complement in the set of sentences, $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}} \setminus \Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$, is computably enumerable, though both are enumerable. Then, more precisely, *the halting set is semidecidable*, see §7¶2.

¶7 · With these tools, we are ready to build uncomputable numbers based on the unsolvability of the halting problem, as B and Ω . So it is time for a new section.

§5 Three complete numbers

§5.1 Computable

¶1 · In **THEOREM 2**, we have used the triangular enumeration of runnings, (\mathbf{c}_c, s) , of the complete language \mathcal{L} to compute the following matrix of bits.

$$\begin{array}{ccccccc} (\mathbf{c}_0, 0) & (\mathbf{c}_0, 1) & \dots & (\mathbf{c}_0, s) & \dots & & \\ (\mathbf{c}_1, 0) & (\mathbf{c}_1, 1) & \dots & (\mathbf{c}_1, s) & \dots & & \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & & \\ (\mathbf{c}_c, 0) & (\mathbf{c}_c, 1) & \dots & (\mathbf{c}_c, s) & \dots & & \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \ddots & & \end{array}$$

DEFINITION: The triangular enumeration of the matrix of runnings defines *number* R , which uses every bit in the matrix, where $i = \nabla(x, y)$ and $(x, y) = \nabla^{-1}(i)$:

$$R = \sum_{i=0}^{\infty} 2^{-(i+1)(\mathbf{c}_x, \mathbf{c}_y)} .$$

¶2 · As number R includes every bit in the matrix of runnings, it could seem that it contains all the information that the halting problem oracle needs, see **Turing (1938)**, suggesting that number R is not computable. However, it is computable!

¶3 · DEFINITION: There are several ways of defining what a computable real number is. **Minsky (1967)**, page 159, defines “a computable number to be one for which there is a Turing machine which, given n on its initial tape, terminates with the n th digit of that number.” Translated to the complete language \mathcal{L} , a number is *computable* if there is a program that, when coded data $\vec{\mathfrak{d}}_n$ is applied to it, it halts with the n th figure of that number coded on the tape. Then, every computable number has to be defined by an *always halting program*, which is one that halts on every (syntactically correct) input.

¶4 · **THEOREM 4**: *Number R is computable.*

PROOF: When computing bit n of number R , the program has first to set the stage, which requires computing $\nabla^{-1}(n) = (c, s)$ and $\nabla^{-1}(c) = (p, d)$, then do the actual running of computation $\mathbf{c}_c = \langle \mathfrak{p}_p | \vec{\mathfrak{d}}_d \rangle$ for s steps, and finally tidy up everything to answer string $\vec{\mathfrak{d}}_1$ if the computation has halted, or string $\vec{\mathfrak{d}}_0$ if it has not halted. Since the program computing number R always (for every $\vec{\mathfrak{d}}_n$) halts after a finite number of computing steps, s plus setup and cleaning, then number R is computable. QED

¶5 · DEFINITION: The *complete numbers* are those that only a universal Turing machine can compute. Then we can also say that the complete numbers can only be defined in a complete language. Numbers B , Ω and R are complete numbers. Loosely speaking, these numbers require a complete language because they cannot be calculated by a single program, given that we need to apply different programs to compute different bits; in fact, to compute a complete number completely we would need to apply all of them.

¶6 · Number R fails to be an uncomputable number because every running is limited to a number of steps, and thus there is no chance of closing an infinite loop. This failure means that the intuitive idea that ‘those numbers that require a complete language to be defined are uncomputable’ does not work. My wrong intuition was that requiring a complete language is the same as requiring self-reference and that self-reference is bound to close infinite loops. We will deal with that intuition below, in §5.3.

§5.2 Uncomputable

¶1 · DEFINITION: We can define an uncomputable *number* H simply by coding the halting computations into a real number between 0 and 1: given a complete language \mathcal{L} with its canonical enumerations $\#$ and ∇ , bit n of number H is 1 if computation \mathfrak{c}_n halts (denoted $\mathfrak{c}_n \downarrow$), and 0 if it does not halt:

$$H = \sum_{\substack{n \in \mathbb{N} \\ n: \mathfrak{c}_n \downarrow}} 2^{-(n+1)} .$$

¶2 · To calculate number H we can start with number 0, that is, with all of its bits set to 0, and following the procedure used to prove that the halting computations are computably enumerable, see [THEOREM 2](#), every time we find a computation \mathfrak{c}_i that halts, $\mathfrak{c}_i \downarrow$, we set bit i to 1. Since the procedure can go on infinitely, we can always add new bits 1 to number H , so we can always make it more precise. However, bits will not be added orderly, that is, having determined that bit j is 1 does not grant us that we could not find later on that another bit $k < j$ is 1. So number H is computably approximable, though it is not left-computable.

¶3 · THEOREM 5: *Number H is not computable.*

PROOF: If number H were computable, then there would be a program that, given coded data $\vec{\mathfrak{d}}_n$ on its initial tape, would halt with the n th bit of number H coded on the tape, let us call it program \mathfrak{h} . Then, computing the n th bit of number H would be done by computation $\langle \mathfrak{h} | \vec{\mathfrak{d}}_n \rangle$, which, if $n = \nabla(p, d)$, would require deciding whether computation $\mathfrak{c}_n = \langle \mathfrak{p}_p | \vec{\mathfrak{d}}_d \rangle$ will halt or not. Since n goes through every natural number and ∇ is a bijection, then program \mathfrak{h} would have to decide for every computation whether it will halt or not. However, the halting theorem says, see [THEOREM 3](#), that such a program \mathfrak{h} cannot exist. Therefore, number H is not computable. QED

¶4 · Should we could compute every bit of number H , then program \mathfrak{h} would exist, but since program \mathfrak{h} cannot exist, then we cannot compute every bit of it. So number H is not computable because we cannot compute *all* of its bits. However, we can compute *some* bits of number H , for example those corresponding to simple computations that halt. Then, number H is not a random number either, since we cannot compute any of the bits of a random number, that is, *none* of them.

¶5 · DEFINITION: Then we will say, by definition, that a number is *unprecise* if we can compute *some* of its bits, where ‘*some*’ means ‘neither *none* nor *all*’. Numbers B , Ω and H are unprecise numbers. Under this definition, the numbers that result from measurements are unprecise, by design; for example, we write 3.25 ± 0.05 m to express purposely that the centimeters digit is random. In this paper, we are not interested on these numbers that are intentionally defined unprecise, so we will only consider those unprecise numbers that are unprecise because of computing limitations.

¶6 · Number H is a complete number, because computing it requires computing every computation. Comparing number H to unprecise numbers B and Ω , number H is more general, since it is not limited to two symbol computations on empty strings. And compared to number Ω , number H is not limited to prefix languages. Number H is the canonical representation of the halting set of the complete language \mathcal{L} implemented by the universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} ; in short, *number H codifies $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$* , the semantics of \mathcal{L} . In still other words, number H is the canonical coding of the halting problem oracle, see [Turing \(1938\)](#), of the complete language \mathcal{L} .

§5.3 Turing's intuition

¶1 · Turing (1936), last paragraph of subsection II of section §9 in page 253, defines the uncomputable number δ :

It must be remembered that we have attached rather a special meaning to the phrase “ \mathfrak{A} defines α ”. The computable numbers do not include all (in the ordinary sense) definable numbers. Let δ be a sequence whose n -th figure is 1 or 0 according as n is or is not satisfactory. It is an immediate consequence of the theorem of §8 that δ is not computable. It is (so far as we know at present) possible that any assigned number of figures of δ can be calculated, but not by a uniform process. When sufficiently many figures of δ have been calculated, an essentially new method is necessary in order to obtain more figures.

¶2 · Here, Turing's method to define the uncomputable number δ was adapted to define our unprecise number H . Instead of satisfactory numbers, which describe non-halting computations, number H uses halting computations, and accordingly it uses the *halting theorem* instead of Turing's theorem of §8. This adaptation updates Turing. In a sense, the adaptation is not necessary, since it just translates (though it is not a full translation, but only a recoding) from the engineering *always running* logic of Turing, where a halted computer with its Blue Screen of Death should be avoided, to the opposite *always halting* logic, which is much more convenient philosophically because it prevents the problems of the infinity.

¶3 · The adaptation is currently so pervasive that Turing's theorem of §8 is usually referred to as the halting theorem without further commentaries or explanations. In what follows, we will assume the *always halting* logic, and consequently, when referring to Turing's unprecise number δ , we should remember that, because of its opposite logic, we have to swap 'running' for 'halting'.

¶4 · In any case, Turing's intuition, as it is expressed in the very last sentence of the cited paragraph, which works for numbers B , Ω , δ and H because all four are complete and unprecise, is not right because it does not work for number R , which is complete and computable. And then it is not always true that needing every possible method in order to obtain more figures makes a number unprecise, and then uncomputable.

¶5 · THEOREM 6: *Not every complete number is unprecise.*

PROOF: Because number R is complete and is not unprecise. It is complete because of its definition, which requires computing every possible computation, and it is computable as shown by THEOREM 4. Being computable, number R is not unprecise. QED

¶6 · I was also wrong believing that every complete number is unprecise, see §5.1¶6. A complete language is one that implements the whole semantics of computing, and therefore it is full-self-expressible, see Casares (G). Then, any concept that requires a complete language to be defined, as for example each complete number, requires the full semantics of computing, including self-reference. Self-reference can easily generate contradictions, the simplest one being the liar paradox, *this sentence is not true*, but, as number R and primitive recursion show, it is not true that every application of self-reference creates a contradiction. In particular, number R shows that keeping finiteness is the proper way for avoiding paradoxes.

§6 Kinds of numbers

§6.1 Naturals

¶1 · How can we classify the numbers from a computing point of view? Let us start from the simplest ones, the counting numbers, also known as the natural numbers, \mathbb{N} .

¶2 · Any natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$ can be written as a finite string of the numerals of the base. In fact, the shortlex order defines a bijection between the strings and the natural numbers, see §3¶1. In base one, which uses only one figure symbol, let us write it 0, the number is represented by the length of the string, so the empty string $\langle \rangle$ represents number zero ($\#\langle \rangle = |\langle \rangle| = 0$), string $\langle 0 \rangle$ represents number one ($\#\langle 0 \rangle = |\langle 0 \rangle| = 1$), string $\langle 00 \rangle$ represents number two ($\#\langle 00 \rangle = |\langle 00 \rangle| = 2$), and so on.

¶3 · In base two, let us use symbols 0 and 1 for the bits, with $0 < 1$, zero is written $\langle \rangle$ ($\#\langle \rangle = 0$), one is written $\langle 0 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 0 \rangle = 1$), two is written $\langle 1 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 1 \rangle = 2$), three is $\langle 00 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 00 \rangle = 3$), four is $\langle 01 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 01 \rangle = 4$), five is $\langle 10 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 10 \rangle = 5$), six $\langle 11 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 11 \rangle = 6$), seven $\langle 000 \rangle$ ($\#\langle 000 \rangle = 7$), and so on.

¶4 · Also in base two, we can use the typical positional notation, which makes easier addition and other operations but which is less compact than our canonical notation, since left zeroes are redundant. In base two positional notation, strings $\langle \rangle$, $\langle 0 \rangle$, $\langle 00 \rangle$, and so on, all represent number zero; one can be written $\langle 1 \rangle$, $\langle 01 \rangle$, $\langle 001 \rangle$ and so on; the shortest way to write two is $\langle 10 \rangle$; and so on.

¶5 · We can continue with base three, four, and so on, but the conclusion is always the same: *any natural number can be written as a finite string of symbols.*

§6.2 Integers

¶1 · Taking any of the notations to write natural numbers, it is enough to add an optional prefix sign, typically a minus symbol ($-$), to write any integer number $z \in \mathbb{Z}$. For example, if in binary positional notation the string $\langle 1101 \rangle$ represents number thirteen, then $\langle -1101 \rangle$ represents minus thirteen.

¶2 · Now the conclusion is: *any integer number can be written as a finite string of symbols.*

§6.3 Rationals

¶1 · Any rational number $q \in \mathbb{Q}$ can be generated by a finite state machine. Disregarding the optional sign symbol, a fraction is simply an ordered pair of natural numbers, so it can be written as two separate finite strings, for instance $23/14$. And, when expanded, every rational numeral, in any natural base, is a regular expression: a finite string for its whole part (\mathbf{w}), a literal point ($.$) separating the whole part from the fractional part, which is a finite prefix string (\mathbf{p}) followed by a infinitely repeated finite string (\mathbf{r}), where the three strings can be empty; a single point represents zero. For example, in positional base ten,

$$\frac{23}{14} = 1.6428571428571428\dots = 1.\overline{6428571},$$

where $\mathbf{w} = \langle 1 \rangle$, $\mathbf{p} = \langle 6 \rangle$, and $\mathbf{r} = \langle 428571 \rangle$, or in general the regular expression $\mathbf{w.p.r}^*$, where the Kleene star $*$ is a postfix meaning *forever*.

¶2 · Therefore a rational number can be expressed as a fraction, which is just an ordered pair of numeral strings, or as its expansion, which is a regular expression. In any case, the conclusion is: *any rational number can be generated by a finite state machine.*

§6.4 Reals

¶1 · That any rational number can be generated by a finite state machine means that the number of states needed to compute any of its bits is limited, and in particular that it does not grow when computing further bits. This is not the case of the irrational numbers, as algebraic $\sqrt{2}$ or transcendental π , which can only be generated by Turing machines with their unbounded tapes. The complete numbers, as B , Ω , δ , R and H , are also irrational numbers, since their expansions are not regular expressions.

¶2 · Computably, the only difference between the algebraic numbers, as $\sqrt{2}$, and the transcendental numbers, as π , is that the programs needed to generate the former ones are somewhat limited, as every algebraic number is the root of a non-zero polynomial in one variable with integer coefficients. Meanwhile, since the transcendental numbers are defined negatively, as those real numbers that are not algebraic, the programs to generate them are not limited. This means that the complete numbers, as B , Ω , δ , R and H , are transcendental. However, in practice the differences between algebraic and transcendental numbers are less clear. For example, infinite series of sums, multiplications and powers of rational numbers can be used to compute both $\sqrt{2}$ and π .

¶3 · Trying to discriminate the unprecise from the computable numbers, there is one thing that is common to our four unprecise numbers, B , Ω , δ and H : all they are complete numbers. However, although it could be intuitive to think that every complete number has to be unprecise, see §5.3, that is not true, as shown by THEOREM 6, which uses number R as counter-example.

¶4 · Following Minsky's definition, see §5.1 ¶3, a number is computable if *all* of its bits are computable, as it is the case of number R . In the other end, a number is random if *none* of its bits is computable; every bit is chosen randomly. And there are also numbers in between, as H , because only *some* of their bits are computable; these are the unprecise numbers, since they cannot be computed with arbitrary precision.

¶5 · In summary, regarding computability, a real number $r \in \mathbb{R}$ can be:

- a *computable number*, as 0 , -13 , $23/14$, $\sqrt{2}$, π or R , which can be computed with arbitrary precision, meaning that we can compute *all* of its bits; or
- a *random number*, which cannot be computed at all, that is, we can compute *none* of its bits, not even one; or, in between,
- an *unprecise number*, as B , Ω , δ or H , which cannot be computed with arbitrary precision, though we can compute *some* of its bits, but neither *none* nor *all* of them.

$$\text{Real} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Computable } \textit{all} \\ \text{Uncomputable} \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \text{Unprecise } \textit{some} \\ \text{Random } \textit{none} \end{array} \right. \end{array} \right.$$

§7 Discussion

¶1 · In any complete language \mathcal{L} , every element is a finite string of the symbols of the corresponding universal Turing machine \mathcal{U} . Then, every set is a set of strings, implying that every set $S \subseteq \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ has a complement, denoted \bar{S} , which is the set of the strings of \mathcal{U} that are not in S , that is, $\bar{S} = \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^* \setminus S$, so $S \cup \bar{S} = \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$ and $S \cap \bar{S} = \emptyset$.

¶2 · Computing classifies sets into three classes.

- Decidable: if *both* itself and its complement are computably enumerable.
- Semidecidable: if only one, *either* itself or its complement, is computably enumerable.
- Undefinable: if *neither* itself nor its complement is computably enumerable.

¶3 · Only those strings that express computations are sentences of \mathcal{L} . The syntax of \mathcal{L} , denoted $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$, is the set of its sentences, so $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}} \subset \Gamma_{\mathcal{U}}^*$, and its complement $\bar{\Sigma}_{\mathcal{L}}$ is the set of the strings that are not sentences of \mathcal{L} . The semantics of \mathcal{L} , denoted $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$, is the set of those sentences that express halting computations, so $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}} \subset \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$, and we say that any sentence that expresses a non-halting computation is a paradox, implying that paradoxes do not belong to semantics. An important property of every complete language \mathcal{L} is that its syntax $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$ is decidable and its semantics $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ is semidecidable, and then undecidable. No program can decide, for every sentence of a complete language, whether it is a paradox or not. Thus, in the Euler diagram of the complete language \mathcal{L} , the limits of semantics $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ are not precise. So while semantics $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ is computably enumerable, neither its complement $\bar{\Psi}_{\mathcal{L}}$ nor the set of paradoxes $\bar{\Psi}_{\mathcal{L}} \cap \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}} = \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}} \setminus \Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$ is computably enumerable.

¶4 · Since the set of coded data strings $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\vec{d}}$ of a complete language \mathcal{L} is enumerable, then there is a bijection between the set of coded data strings and the natural numbers, $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\vec{d}} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$, meaning that any natural number $n \in \mathbb{N}$ can be coded into a string $\vec{d}_n \in \Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\vec{d}}$, and the converse, $\vec{d}_n \leftrightarrow n$. There are also bijections between the integer and the natural numbers, $\mathbb{Z} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$, and, using the triangular enumeration, between the rational and the natural numbers, $\mathbb{Q} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$. That $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}^{\vec{d}} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{Z} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{Q}$ means that the syntax of any complete language is enough to code all of these numbers.

¶5 · In the case of the real numbers, **Cantor (1891)** showed that there is not any bijection between the real and the natural numbers; the bijection is between the real numbers and the sets of natural numbers, $\mathbb{R} \leftrightarrow 2^{\mathbb{N}}$. This means that, in computing, each real number has to be coded into a set of finite strings. Notice that for coding an irrational number, with its non-repeating infinite expansion, the set has to be infinite. And notice also that we can express a finite set as the complete list of all of its members, but that in order to define an infinite set we need a program that enumerates it. Being defined on the behavior of programs, the irrational numbers require semantics. So, while syntax is enough to express the rational numbers, the irrational numbers need semantics to define them, and even the whole of semantics to define the complete numbers.

¶6 · Syntax is binary but there is a third possibility when semantics is involved. Therefore, as with sets, computing classifies the real numbers into three classes.

- Computable: if its coding set is decidable. All natural, integer and rational numbers are computable. Some irrational numbers are computable, for example numbers $\sqrt{2}$, π and R . The computable numbers can be defined and expressed, fully. Most used real numbers are computable.
- Unprecise: if its coding set is semidecidable. Numbers B , Ω , δ and H , which are defined on the semidecidable halting set, are unprecise. The unprecise numbers can be defined but they cannot be fully expressed, since they cannot be specified to the bit, so they are semiparadoxical oddities among the real numbers.
- Random: if its coding set is undefinable. You can generate a random number but, once you have generated it, it is not random anymore; as soon as it has been fully expressed, it is already computable. Although most real numbers are random, they cannot be conceptualized because they are undefinable.

§8 Conclusion

¶1 · In computing, a natural, an integer or a rational number can be coded into a finite string. However, a real number has to be coded into a set of finite strings. For this reason, we can classify the real numbers the same way we classify the sets: computable or decidable, unprecise or semidecidable, and random or undefinable.

¶2 · The halting set is the canonical semidecidable set, and then all our unprecise numbers — B , Ω , H and δ — are defined on it. And all four are also complete numbers because, in order to compute all of the bits of any of them, we would need to compute every program. So Turing believed that his number δ is not computable because we would need to compute every program in order to compute all of its bits. We show that, in this case, Turing's intuition was wrong, because our number R , which codes the decidable set of runnings, is both complete and computable.

¶3 · Let me conclude answering our first question: Why do not we use, in practice, any uncomputable number? We know now that we can define and use the unprecise numbers, which are classified as uncomputable though they are, more precisely, semicomputable. In any case, since the unprecise numbers are few (relative to the random ones) and seldom used (relative to the computable ones), considering them either computable or uncomputable does not affect my answer, which follows, save for adding some detail.

¶4 · Should we were able to calculate beyond what is computable, then we would use, whenever we should see fit, super-computable numbers, which would be those numbers that are beyond what is computable, that is, the uncomputable numbers. Therefore, either

- we cannot calculate what is not computable, or
- the uncomputable numbers are useless.

I think the first case, which derives from the law of Post, is true, see [Casares \(C\)](#), which would explain why Church's thesis was not yet refuted. If I am right about this, then the second case is inconsequential, even though it is likely false, since there are infinitely many more uncomputable than computable numbers. And, consequently, my answer is that we do not use uncomputable numbers because, being under the law of Post, *we cannot calculate what is not computable*.

Theorems

Theorem 1: *The set of all computations is computably enumerable*

Theorem 2: *The set of all halting computations is computably enumerable*

Theorem 3: *No program can decide for every computation whether it will halt or not*

Corollary: *In every complete language, syntax is decidable but semantics is undecidable*

Theorem 4: *Number R is computable*

Theorem 5: *Number H is not computable*

Theorem 6: *Not every complete number is unprecise*

Definitions

always halting program (§5.1¶3) one that halts on every (syntactically correct) input

complete language (§3¶4) \mathcal{L} , also known as Turing complete language

complete number (§5.1¶5) only a universal Turing machine can compute it

computable number (§5.1¶3) all of its bits are computable

computation (§3¶4) $\mathbf{c} = \langle \mathbf{p} | \vec{\mathbf{d}} \rangle$, applying coded data $\vec{\mathbf{d}}$ to program \mathbf{p}

equation of Turing completeness (§3¶3) there is a universal Turing machine \mathcal{U}

halting set (§3¶4) $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$, the set of the halting computations of complete language \mathcal{L}

halting theorem (§4¶1) is Theorem 3

number B (§2¶2) Radó's busy beaver maximum shifts number

number δ (§5.3¶1) Turing's uncomputable number

number H (§5.2¶1) halting number of complete language \mathcal{L}

number R (§5.1¶1) runnings number of complete language \mathcal{L}

number Ω (§2¶3) Chaitin's constant

paradox (§3¶5) a non-halting computation

program (§3¶3) $\mathbf{p} = \vec{\mathcal{P}}$, Turing machine \mathcal{P} coded in complete language \mathcal{L}

random number (§2¶4) none of its bits is computable

running (§3¶7) (\mathbf{c}, s) , computing s steps of computation \mathbf{c}

semantics (§3¶5) is the halting set, $\Psi_{\mathcal{L}}$

shortlex order (§3¶1) bijection between strings and natural numbers $\# : \Gamma^* \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$

syntax (§3¶5) $\Sigma_{\mathcal{L}}$, the set of the sentences of complete language \mathcal{L}

triangular enumeration (§3¶2) Cantor's pairing bijection $\nabla : \mathbb{N} \times \mathbb{N} \leftrightarrow \mathbb{N}$

unprecise number (§5.2¶5) some of its bits are computable

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